



Fig. A.1. Same as Fig. 2 but for the F5 fields.



Fig. A.2. Same as Fig. 2 but for the F3 fields.



Fig. A.3. Same as Fig. 2 but for the F2 fields.



Fig. A.4. Same as Fig. 3 but for the F5 fields.



Fig. A.5. Same as Fig. 3 but for the F3 fields.



Fig. A.6. Same as Fig. 3 but for the F2 fields.



Fig. A.7. Same as Fig. 3 but for the F1 fields.



Fig. A.8. Same as Fig. 4 but for the F5 fields.



Fig. A.9. Same as Fig. 4 but for the F3 fields.



Fig. A.10. Same as Fig. 4 but for the F2 fields.



Fig. A.11. Same as Fig. 4 but for the F1 fields.



Fig. A.12. Same as Fig. 5 but for the F5 fields.



Fig. A.13. Same as Fig. 5 but for the F3 fields.



Fig. A.14. Same as Fig. 5 but for the F2 fields.



Fig. A.15. Same as Fig. 5 but for the F1 fields.



Fig. A.16. Same as Fig. 6 but for the F5 fields.



Fig. A.17. Same as Fig. 6 but for the F3 fields.



Fig. A.18. Same as Fig. 6 but for the F2 fields.



Fig. A.19. Same as Fig. 6 but for the F1 fields.